

TECHNOLOGIES OF USING READING COMPREHENSION EXERCISES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATION COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: The presented article discusses the issue of using grammar exercises in reading classes, which is of great importance in our development of technologies for using reading comprehension exercises to improve communication competences of English philology students..

Keywords: Communicative competence, Reading comprehension exercises, Technologies of using reading exercises, grammar, syntactic structure, grammar exercises, discourse.

It is an important task of the teacher to read and understand the reading material, to learn new words in the text, to expand their worldview, to learn the learning material in the lesson and to motivate them to study outside the class, to improve their creative and critical thinking, and to be able to choose the exercises and assignments correctly in the development of communication competences of the students. Before organizing a study session and selecting effective exercises, consider the following. Until recently, reading materials focused on sentences and sentence fragments. The text is viewed as a sequence of thematically connected sentences, and therefore the task is to understand the meaning and structure of each sentence in the text. However, in order for the reading process to be effective, it is necessary to focus on the content of longer passages, such as paragraphs, rather than sentences. Studying a text as a set of independent sentences, regardless of the purpose of reading, makes the student dependent on understanding the meaning of each sentence in the text. As a result, the student pays the same attention to each sentence of the text and does not develop independent inference skills during reading. It is clear from this that reading should focus first on the general content and then on the small details. Exercises related to the given text are also given based on this sequence: first, tasks defining the content, function and purpose of the text, then tasks on vocabulary and other ideas.

When developing technologies for using exercises that develop reading skills, it is appropriate to study the importance of grammar, vocabulary, discursive structure of the text, and reading strategies that help reading

comprehension in the process of reading and understanding the main idea in the text, and to select exercises based on this knowledge. Understanding the text, understanding the main content requires identifying the main ideas in the text, being able to integrate them with the text model of reading and creating an appropriate situational model of the student's interpretation. To understand the content of the text, it is necessary to have sufficient initial grammatical knowledge, to know effective reading comprehension strategies for working with difficult texts, to develop data analysis skills to maintain a high level of comprehension for a long time, to know discourse structure, and to have a large receptive vocabulary base.

"It is hard to believe that reading comprehension does not require syntactic analysis." The role of grammar in reading comprehension is not a common topic in reading books. The separation of reading and grammar may be due to the lack of emphasis on grammar in approaches based on the communicative approach, or the concern that reading should not become a grammar lesson. Some Methodists, on the other hand, are skeptical about the importance of grammatical knowledge in understanding the content of the text. We do not have enough knowledge about the role of grammar in helping understanding. In fact, there are many reasons why grammar is so important to reading comprehension. Grammatical and syntactic knowledge during reading, syntactic analysis is not considered a necessary linguistic knowledge or analysis technique. Analysis of text fragments to obtain structural information that supports reading comprehension occurs every second of the fluent reading process. A student with a high level of English will not pay attention to this process. A student with insufficient knowledge of grammar immediately faces difficulties. Much research in speech analysis and language comprehension argues that syntax and reading are related. Neshn and Bowie cite research on the effects of syntactic knowledge on reading ability. Bowie (1995), Bryan, McLean and Bradley (1990), Demon and Gombert (1996), Gox (1999), Neshn and Snowling (2000), Scarborough (1990) and many other scientists have shown that syntactic knowledge, analysis ability (processing skills) shows that it is related to reading comprehension and difficulties in it. As soon as the reader begins to look at the text, the process of visual word recognition begins, the first words are recognized, and the extraction of syntactic information begins. Syntactic processing (syntactic processing) constructs phrases and clauses that help make semantic sentences. Structural information is derived from familiar words, and specific groups of words are distinguished by the structural

information they provide. For example, the article means that a clause with a noun phrase is coming, and the verb put indicates that a noun phrase and a locative prepositional phrase are coming after it.

Syntactic processing supports other types of data and analysis that are important for understanding:

1. clarifying processes (negation of alternative meanings, activation of semantic priming within fragments that spreads to all lexical elements within the phrase);
2. identifying referents (pronouns, demonstrative pronouns, articles);
3. standard processing techniques (such as the expected placement of the possessive-partial-complement, multiple occurrences of certain sentence structures).

(1) As words are recognized and syntax is processed, the meaning of clauses and sentences is also constructed. Activated words and information from syntactic analysis are integrated into meaningful chunks. In this way, words and grammatical structures provide the reader with the necessary information to reveal the content of the text.

(2) Grammar provides the reader with clues about how to interpret sentences and how to connect the sentences to the meaning network of the text being constructed. Grammatical information shows us how to understand the content, the relevance of the content to the ongoing discourse. To understand how sentence-level information works in content comprehension, consider the following example. (1) the sentence provides content words, but it is not clear what the content of the sentence is:

(3) *new, think, police, students, run, money, they, car*

If we put the words in the right order, the reader will get more information. In English, word order is a key tool in understanding the language:

(4) *new students, think, money, they, run, the police car*

How much help the reader can get with just one word order, but we don't have much information. In the next sentence, let's put the articles in their place:

(5) *The new students, think, the money, they, run, the police car*

Now the reader knows that three of the nouns have been identified through the previous discourse. By adding tense and aspect, we learn that events happened in the past tense:

(4) *The new students, have thought, the money, they, ran, the police car*

Let's add a modality hint to this sentence:

(5) *The new students might have thought, the money, they ran, the police car*

We do not know how the two actions are related to each other and how the possessive and participle are connected. Ravish explained that when we add the conjunction as a cue, both actions occur simultaneously, and the relationship between the prepositions thought and the money and the location and direction of the second event.

(6) The new students might have thought about the money while they ran to the police car

It can be seen that any aspect of grammatical information provides clarity to the meaning of the sentence by reducing ambiguity.

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